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ANALYSIS OF DIRECTIONS OF MODERNIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS OF THE EDUCATIONAL SECTOR

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Conceptual and legal bases of formation and realization of educational policy of Ukraine are considered. The vector of educational policy is aimed at its modernization and promotion of broad cooperation with educational institutions, research institutions, public organizations, private foundations of the European educational space, representation of Ukraine's interests in education and science in international relations in the prescribed manner.

Four key objectives of European cooperation in the field of higher education have been identified: addressing future skills mismatches and promoting skills development; building inclusive and integrated higher education systems; providing higher education institutions that promote innovation; support for efficient and effective higher education systems.

The political and legal aspects of cooperation between Ukraine and the EU in the field of education and the involvement of our country in the formation of the European educational space have been clarified.

The main tendencies of professional training of specialists in the field of education are determined. These are: lifelong learning, development of professional skills and qualifications, entrepreneurship formation, quality assurance in higher education, optimization of management and funding.

The modernization of the national system of professional training of specialists in the field of education, namely: establishing direct relations of universities with foreign partners on cooperation in the field of professional training of specialists in the field of education, concluding and ensuring implementation of international agreements on training, re-training and advanced training of foreign citizens at educational institutions of Ukraine

Keywords: *European educational space, European Union (EU), EU educational policy, modernization, professional training*

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1. Introduction

The study is caused by the growing global challenges, facing the world economy today, the growing impact of the global labor market and educational services, risks and threats, facing the Ukrainian economy in recent years, the development of new generation technologies, exacerbation of demographic and social problems and more. The importance of researching the directions of modernization of professional training of specialists in the field of education is also due to European integration aspirations, expanding cooperation in the field of education and prospects for implementing the positive experience of the European educational space in Ukraine.

The European vector of Ukraine, enshrined in the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the European Union (2014), intensifies the synchronization of Ukraine with European standards. In this context, the integration of Ukrainian education into the European educational space is taking place, which involves the formation of a European-oriented national educational policy.

Peculiarities of formation and implementation of educational policy of Ukraine are studied mostly in the context of the formation of the Bologna process. However, it is also necessary to study the legal mechanisms for

regulating the educational policy of Ukraine on the basis of general principles of forming common policies of the EEC countries and their activities. It is important to identify ways to modernize the training of education professionals through the study of positive European experience, which determines the relevance of the study.

2. Literature review

Many Ukrainian and foreign researchers are interested in Ukraine's European integration in the field of education. A number of works by scientists I. Ivanyuk [1], O. Kraevska [2], O. Lokshina [3], S. Sysoeva, T. Krystopchuk [4] are devoted to this topic; political scientists (Vilchynska N.Yu. [5]) and others.

Analyzing the reform of the British education system, Ivanyuk I. points out the importance of controlling the quality of education. The country's control over the quality of education standards in England is carried out by a special government department of education – The Office for Standards in Education (OFSTED), which was restored in 1993 and is headed by the Chief Inspector of Her Majesty's Inspectorate [1].

Kraevska O. considers the conceptual and legal bases of formation and implementation of the educational

policy of the European Union and investigates the institutional and legal mechanisms of functioning of the educational policy of the EU. The researcher notes the importance of participation in international educational programs [2]:

- Tempus program;
- Erasmus Mundus Program;
- Jean Monnet program

Lokshina O. emphasizes the synchronization of the national system of quality assurance in higher education in Ukraine with its European counterpart. A mandatory component of quality assurance in higher education should be constant monitoring of achievements and shortcomings [3].

Sysoeva S. and Krystopchuk T. [4] identified trends that dominate the structure of European higher education. Emphasis is placed on creating an effective system of control and adequate assessment of the quality of educational curricula, standardization of education on the transfer system of European credits, aimed at increasing student mobility, implementation of the general system of degrees, active participation of students and teachers in higher education programs and projects, organization of international research and dissemination of innovative approaches to pedagogical education.

In her research, N. Vilchynska, a political scientist, notes that “education and training are no longer constrained by national frameworks, the new learning society should potentially be formed not from citizens of European Union member states, bearers of a certain culture and history, but from European individuals who have the desire and ability to learn for life. Thus, the EU has transferred the responsibility for obtaining, quality of education and employment from the state to each individual personally [5].

However, it is important to identify a set of ways to modernize the training of education professionals in Ukraine.

Among Western European researchers, Karlsen Gustav E., who studies educational policy issues in the European Union, is worth noting [6].

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The purpose of this article is to study the directions of modernization of professional training of specialists in the field of education in the process of using the European experience.

To achieve this goal, it is needed to analyze:

- normative-legal documents of Ukraine on professional training of specialists in the field of education, as well as in the countries of the European educational space;
- identification of ways to modernize the system of professional training of specialists in the field of education in Ukraine;
- outlining the prospects of development of professional training of specialists in the field of education.

4. Materials and methods

In the process of scientific research general scientific methods were used - analysis, synthesis, systematization of documents, legislative acts to substantiate the initial positions of scientists and practitioners on the re-

search problem. Using the chronological-systemic method, the legal framework for the training of specialists in the field of education in Ukraine and the countries of the European educational space was considered.

5. Result

5.1. Analysis of the legal framework of Ukraine and the countries of the European educational space for the training of specialists in the field of education

The purpose of national education and training is to integrate into the European educational space, in the process of which there should be qualitative changes in the organization of the educational process in order to train competitive professionals for the labor market. The tasks of higher education are defined in the Laws "On Education" [7], "On Higher Education" [8], "On Priority Areas of Science and Technology" [9]; decrees of the President of Ukraine "On the National Doctrine of Education Development" [10]; scientific and pedagogical bases – in concepts; ways of realization – in normative documents. These legislative documents create a real field for the development of professional training of specialists in the field of education and science in Ukraine.

Adaptation of Ukrainian legislation to European is based on the signed Agreement on Partnership and Cooperation with EU countries [11]. This agreement provides a legal basis for the development of professional training based on the principles of democracy and human rights, as well as establishes political, economic and trade relations between the European Union and Ukraine.

Thus, the legal, economic and organizational principles of state policy in the field of education are defined by law; legally outlined social guarantees for the realization of citizens' rights to education; defined the state policy in the field of higher education; laid the foundations of state support of science and scientific and technical policy as development, rational use of the scientific and technical potential, increasing the contribution of science and technology to the development of state economy, implementation of social tasks.

The importance of adapting Ukrainian legislation on professional training to the European one is caused by the need to integrate the national education system into the international educational space. In the context of the above, the Law of Ukraine "On the National Program for Adaptation of the Legislation of Ukraine to the Legislation of the European Union" was developed and adopted [12].

It is noted, that higher education and its links to research and innovation play a crucial role in individual and societal development, as well as in providing the highly skilled human capital and employed citizens Europe needs for jobs, economic growth and prosperity. Higher education institutions are key partners in implementing the European Union's strategy to move forward and support sustainable growth. It should be noted, that the document emphasizes the need for sustainable and substantial investment, for which the authorities of the Member States are responsible. EU action is designed to provide an additional international dimension to the study, teaching, research or policy-making in higher education.

Through its Erasmus + and Horizon 2020 programs, the European Union supports the international exchange of students, teachers and researchers, as well as structured cooperation between higher education institutions and public authorities in different countries [13].

The aim is to create new opportunities for higher education students to learn from each other across national borders and to work together on joint projects to develop good teaching and learning, conduct research and promote them [13].

The European Commission works closely with policymakers to support the development of higher education policies in the EU in line with the Education and Training 2020 strategy (ET2020). The updated EU agenda for higher education, adopted by the Commission in May 2017, sets out four key objectives for European cooperation in higher education [14]:

- solving the problems of inconsistency of future skills and promoting the improvement of skills development;
- building inclusive and connected higher education systems;
- providing higher education institutions to promote innovation;
- support for efficient and effective higher education systems.

5. 2. Regulatory framework for the training of education professionals in Ukraine

To help achieve each of these goals, the Commission proposes concrete actions at EU level, primarily with the support of the various strands of Erasmus + and Horizon 2020. In particular, the European Commission supports [14]:

- exchange of good policy practices between different countries through the ET2020 Higher Education Working Group;
- The Bologna Process, designed to promote the internationalization of higher education in Europe due to greater mobility, simplification of recognition of qualifications and streamlined quality assurance mechanisms;
- developing and using mobility and recognition tools, such as the ECTS system and the Diploma Supplement, to increase transparency and the exchange of services in Europe.

In the context of the European Education Area, the European Commission has taken a number of further initiatives:

- the concept of European university networks makes significant changes in higher education practices through integrated curricula and mobility, thus contributing to quality, excellence and innovation;
- the Council's proposed recommendation on the automatic mutual recognition of higher education and school diplomas helps to remove barriers to student mobility in Europe;
- The future European student card will facilitate the secure exchange of student information and reduce the administrative burden for higher education institutions, serving as a concrete example of the formation of the European educational space.

The priority areas of state policy for the development of education are: personal orientation of education;

formation of national and universal values; constant improvement of the quality of education, updating of its content and forms of organization of the educational process; development of a system of continuing vocational education and lifelong learning; integration of domestic education into the European and world educational space.

Vital today is the development of a system of professional training in the context of the paradigm of continuing professional education.

The task, facing the training of specialists, is to constantly update the content of education and the organization of the educational process in accordance with democratic values, market principles of the economy, modern scientific and technological achievements.

Particular attention is paid to the need to significantly strengthen the educational material base, the computerization of educational institutions, the introduction of information technology, effective training and retraining of teachers and research and teaching staff, the introduction of new economic and management mechanisms for education. The solution of these problems will provide accelerated, advanced innovative development of education, as well as create conditions for the development, self-affirmation and self-realization of the individual throughout life.

An important component of the development of professional training is to identify ways to involve employers in the educational process [8].

Thus, the analysis of national legislation and regulations shows that the training of education professionals is recognized as one of the priorities of public policy.

The analysis of the experience of professional training in the EU countries allowed to determine the ways of modernization of professional training in Ukraine as follows:

- the presence of flexibility both in the curriculum and in the management structure;
- creation of creative associations with stakeholders;
- staffing development;
- development of relations with other countries to deepen knowledge;
- application of management practices that rely on partnerships with external stakeholders;
- implementation of flexible forms of personnel management, including incentives and personnel development programs;
- a variety of sources of funding, in particular by increasing revenues through the expansion of services.

Among the latest trends in the system of professional training are the consolidation of the structure, the emergence of new interdisciplinary educational tasks, diversification of services, focus on innovation, a more globalized nature of science, changing the role of information and the Internet as one of its main sources.

Modernization of the national system of professional training can also be solved through the introduction of modern information technology.

Innovative forms of continuing vocational education include a mixed form of education.

The main factors, influencing the organization of a system of blended learning, are socio-economic. More-

over, social factors play an important role due to the need for higher education and training and retraining, increasing the number of students who want to work while studying. The main ways to modernize the training of specialists in Ukraine can be:

- creation of university specialized distance learning centers;
- expansion of forms of education through the development of curricula for blended learning;
- dissemination of cooperation and integration processes (creation of associations of universities, national and interregional distance learning centers);

Changing the strategic goals of education requires a shift of emphasis from the acquisition of knowledge of the specialist to his/her personal qualities, which provide lifelong learning.

5. 3. Areas of cooperation between Ukraine and the EU in the training of professionals with the experience of the EU

Socio-economic transformations in Ukraine have led to the need to modernize the training of specialists, which would meet the current requirements of both professional and social activities. The use of the experience of EU countries in vocational training in Ukraine shows that the main tasks of further modernization of vocational training in Ukraine is to intensify cooperation between Ukraine and the European Education Area in vocational training [15].

The analysis of the normative-legal base of professional training of specialists testifies to the adaptation of the Ukrainian legislation to the European one, respectively, to the signed Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between Ukraine and the European Communities and their member states. The main task of the national legislation on professional training is to enshrine at the legislative level the requirements and conditions for the quality of educational services that provide material and spiritual aspirations of educational entities.

The importance of adapting Ukrainian legislation on professional training to the European one is caused by the need to integrate the national education system into the international educational space. In the context of the above, the country has developed and adopted the Law of Ukraine "On the National Program for Adaptation of the Legislation of Ukraine to the Legislation of the European Union" (2004). The detailed elaboration of the current legislative and regulatory framework has shown that this range of issues, related to the participation of employers in training and retraining, educational and scientific processes, are governed by current laws of Ukraine, in particular "On Education", "On Higher Education", "On scientific and scientific-technical activities".

The results of the analysis of scientific works and legal documents are presented, in which the development of professional training of specialists in the field of education is developed, which allowed us to determine the directions of its modernization. It covers the human resources of higher education institutions, ensuring the quality of education, information resources, the results of integration into the European educational space.

Further research work on the problems of modernization of professional training of specialists in the field of education in Ukraine requires the development of a strategy for lifelong learning and mobility; encouraging cooperation between higher education institutions of Ukraine, cooperation with foreign educational institutions, stakeholders.

6. Conclusions

1. The analysis of the legal framework for the training of specialists in the field of education shows that educational policy is considered as a system of organization of the educational process, as an organic component of the socio-political organization of the European Union. It is adapted to the European one. The legislation of the countries of the European educational space defines the key goals of European cooperation, among which the main priority is the promotion of innovation. The European Union's education policy is the international cooperation of government and educational institutions of the EU member states to achieve common goals: increase the EU's competitiveness in the political arena, create an efficient knowledge-based economy, ensure a high level of education, create conditions for better mobility in higher education. EU, training of specialists in demand for economic purposes, optimization of national education policy systems, attraction of scientific potential from neighboring countries to the European community through participation in educational programs, etc.

2. Ways of modernization of professional training of specialists in the field of education are determined by:

- introduction of an interdisciplinary approach into the educational process;
- introduction of a mixed form of education into the educational process;
- establishing partnerships with external stakeholders;
- involvement of employers in the educational process;
- diversification of sources of funding for higher education institutions.

3. Prospects for the development of professional training of specialists in the field of education in Ukraine are:

- creation of structures, responsible for strategic forecasting of educational and qualification needs of the labor market at both national and regional levels;
- development and implementation of effective for Ukraine modern methods of strategic forecasting of educational and qualification needs of the labor market;
- determination of priority directions of professional training of specialists in the field of education;
- wide involvement of employers in the process of professional training of specialists of different educational levels at all stages of the process: planning the scope and directions of training, creating training programs, employment after graduation, retraining and advanced training in the process of professional activity.

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